

GENERALIZATION OF UNIVERSAL PARTITION AND BIPARTITION THEOREMS

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Abstract

Let $A = (a_{i,j})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, be an infinite matrix with elements $a_{i,j} = 0$ or 1 ; $p(n, k; A)$ the number of partitions of n into k parts whose number y_i of parts which are equal to i belongs to the set $Y_i = \{j : a_{i,j} = 1\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$. The universal theorem on partitions states that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n p(n, k; A) u^k t^n = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_{i,j} u^j t^{ij} \right).$$

In this paper, we present a generalization of this result. We show that this generalization remains true when $a_{i,j}$ are indeterminate. We also take into account the bi-partite and multi-partite situations.

1. Introduction

Let $A = (a_{i,j})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ be an infinite matrix with elements $a_{i,j} = 0$ or 1 ; $p(n, k; A)$ the number of partitions of n into k parts whose number y_i of parts which are equal to i belongs to the set $Y_i = \{j : a_{i,j} = 1\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$. The universal theorem on partitions states that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n p(n, k; A) u^k \right) t^n = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_{i,j} u^j t^{ij} \right); \quad (1)$$

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see for instance [2] and [3].

In Section 2, we will provide an extension of the above identity and show that it remains true when $a_{i,j}$ are indeterminate. In Section 3, we will present an equivalent version in terms of complete Bell polynomials when $a_{i,0} = 1, i \geq 1$.

Similarly, a partition of an ordered pair $(m, n) \neq (0, 0)$, of nonnegative integers, is a non-ordered collection of nonnegative integers $(x_i, y_i) \neq (0, 0), i = 1, 2, \dots$, whose sum equals (m, n) . Given a partition of (m, n) , let $k_{i,j}$ be the number of parts which are equal to $(i, j), i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, (i, j) \neq (0, 0)$, such that

$$\sum_{i=0}^m i \sum_{j=0}^n k_{i,j} = m, \quad \sum_{j=0}^n j \sum_{i=0}^m k_{i,j} = n. \tag{2}$$

For a partition of (m, n) into k parts, we add

$$\sum_{i=0}^m \sum_{j=0}^n k_{i,j} = k. \tag{3}$$

Let $p(m, n)$ be the number of partitions of the bi-partite number (m, n) with $p(0, 0) = 1$ and $p(m, n, k)$ be the number of partitions of (m, n) into k parts with $p(0, 0, 0) = 1$. The universal bipartition theorem states that

$$F(t, u, w) = \sum_{m,n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m+n} p(m, n, k) w^k \right) t^m u^n = \prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ (i,j) \neq (0,0)}}^{\infty} \prod_{i=0}^{\infty} (1 - wt^i u^j)^{-1}; \tag{4}$$

see [2, p. 403, pb. 24]. A generalization of identity (4) is dealt with in Section 4. Section 5 is devoted to the concept of multipartition.

2. Generalized Universal Partition Theorem

Theorem 1. Let $X = (x_{i,j}), i = 1, 2, \dots, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, be an infinite matrix of indeterminates; $\pi(n, k)$ the set of all nonnegative integer solutions of

$$k_1 + k_2 + \dots + k_n = k \quad \text{and} \quad k_1 + 2k_2 + \dots + nk_n = n;$$

and $\pi(n) = \bigcup_{k=1}^n \pi(n, k)$ be the set of all nonnegative integer solutions of $k_1 + 2k_2 + \dots + nk_n = n$. For every solution $k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n$, we set

$$p(n, k; X) := \sum_{\pi(n,k)} x_{1,k_1} x_{2,k_2} \dots x_{n,k_n}.$$

Then

$$G(t, u; X) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n p(n, k; X) u^k \right) t^n = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} x_{i,j} u^j t^{ij} \right).$$

Proof. We have

$$G(t, u; X) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n \left(\sum_{\pi(n,k)} x_{1,k_1} x_{2,k_2} \cdots x_{n,k_n} u^{k_1+\cdots+k_n} t^{k_1+2k_2+\cdots+nk_n} \right).$$

Since these sums apply for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, n$ and $n = 0, 1, \dots$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} G(t, u; X) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n \left(\sum_{\pi(n,k)} (x_{1,k_1} (ut)^{k_1}) (x_{2,k_2} (ut^2)^{k_2}) \cdots (x_{n,k_n} (ut^n)^{k_n}) \right) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{\pi(n)} (x_{1,k_1} (ut)^{k_1}) (x_{2,k_2} (ut^2)^{k_2}) \cdots (x_{n,k_n} (ut^n)^{k_n}) \right) \\ &= \left(\sum_{k_1=0}^{\infty} x_{1,k_1} (ut)^{k_1} \right) \left(\sum_{k_2=0}^{\infty} x_{2,k_2} (ut^2)^{k_2} \right) \cdots \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} x_{i,j} (ut^i)^j \right), \end{aligned}$$

which is the required expression. □

For $x_{i,j} = a_{i,j}$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, in Theorem 1, we obtain the universal theorem on partitions. For $x_{i,j} = \frac{a_{i,j}}{j!j^j}$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, in Theorem 1, we obtain:

Corollary 2. *Let $A = (a_{i,j})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, be an infinite matrix with elements $a_{i,j} = 0$ or 1 and $c(n, k; A)$ the number of permutations of a finite set W_n , of n elements, that are decomposed into k cycles such that the number of cycles of length i belongs to the set $Y_i = \{j : a_{i,j} = 1\}$. Then*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n c(n, k; A) u^k \frac{t^n}{n!} = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} a_{i,j} \frac{u^j}{j!} \left(\frac{t^i}{i} \right)^j \right).$$

For $x_{i,j} = \frac{1}{j!} \left(\frac{z_i}{i!} \right)^j a_{i,j}$, $z_i \in \mathbb{C}, i = 1, 2, \dots, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, in Theorem 1, we obtain a remarkable identity according to the partial Bell polynomials:

Corollary 3. *Let $A = (a_{i,j})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, be an infinite matrix with elements $a_{i,j} = 0$ or 1 and*

$$B_{n,k;A}(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) := \sum_{\pi(n,k)} \frac{n!}{k_1! \cdots k_n!} \left(\frac{z_1}{1!} \right)^{k_1} \cdots \left(\frac{z_n}{n!} \right)^{k_n} a_{1,k_1} \cdots a_{n,k_n}.$$

Then we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n B_{n,k;A}(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) u^k \frac{t^n}{n!} = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_{i,j}}{j!} \left(u z_i \frac{t^i}{i!} \right)^j \right).$$

Remark 4. For $a_{i,j} = 1$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$ and $j = 0, 1, \dots$, Corollary 3 gives

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n B_{n,k}(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) u^k \frac{t^n}{n!} = \exp \left(u \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} z_i \frac{t^i}{i!} \right),$$

which is the definition of the partial Bell polynomials $B_{n,k}(z_1, \dots, z_n)$. See [1, 3, 4].

3. Connection With the Complete Bell Polynomials

Recall that the complete Bell polynomials $A_n(x_1, x_2, \dots)$ are defined by

$$\sum_{n=k}^{\infty} A_n(x_1, x_2, \dots) \frac{t^n}{n!} = \exp \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} x_m \frac{t^m}{m!} \right).$$

See [1, 3, 4].

In this section, we provide another formulation of Theorem 1 according to the complete Bell polynomials. We determine the generating functions of the sequences $(p(n, k; X))_n$ and $(p(n, k; X))_k$, where $X = (x_{i,j})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, is an infinite matrix with indeterminates $x_{i,j}$ such that $x_{i,0} = 1$ for every $i \geq 1$.

Theorem 5. Let q, u be indeterminate. Then, for $n \geq 1$, we have

$$\sum_{j=n}^{\infty} p(j, n; X) q^j = \frac{1}{n!} A_n(\rho_1(q; X), \rho_2(q; X), \dots, \rho_n(q; X)), \tag{5}$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^n p(n, j; X) u^j = \frac{1}{n!} A_n(\sigma_1(u; X), \sigma_2(u; X), \dots, \sigma_n(u; X)), \tag{6}$$

where

$$\rho_n(q; X) := \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} b_n(i) q^{ni} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_n(u; X) := n! \sum_{k|n} b_k \left(\frac{n}{k} \right) \frac{u^k}{k!},$$

with

$$b_n(i) = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} (k-1)! B_{n,k}(1!x_{i,1}, 2!x_{i,2}, \dots, j!x_{i,j}, \dots).$$

Proof. From Theorem 1, we get

$$G(q, u; X) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n p(n, k; X) u^k q^n = \exp \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \ln \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (j! x_{i,j}) \frac{(uq^i)^j}{j!} \right) \right).$$

Using the following known expansion (see [2, Theorem 11.17])

$$\ln \left(1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} g_k \frac{q^k}{k!} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_n \frac{q^n}{n!},$$

with $c_n = \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} (k-1)! B_{n,k}(g_1, g_2, \dots)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} G(q, u; X) &= \exp \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k(i) \frac{u^k}{k!} q^{ki} \right) = \exp \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{u^k}{k!} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} b_k(i) q^{ki} \right) \\ &= \exp \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \rho_k(q; X) \frac{u^k}{k!} \right) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k(\rho_1(q; X), \dots, \rho_k(q; X)) \frac{u^k}{k!}. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we have

$$G(q, u; X) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^n p(n, k; X) u^k q^n = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=k}^{\infty} p(n, k; X) q^n \right) u^k.$$

The first identity follows from identification, where as the second identity follows from the expansion

$$\begin{aligned} G(q, u; X) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n p(n, k; X) u^k \right) q^n \\ &= \exp \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \ln \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (j! x_{i,j}) \frac{(uq^i)^j}{j!} \right) \right) \\ &= \exp \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k(i) u^k \frac{q^{ik}}{k!} \right) \\ &= \exp \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q^n \sum_{k|n} b_k \left(\frac{n}{k} \right) \frac{u^k}{k!} \right) \\ &= \exp \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_n(u; X) \frac{q^n}{n!} \right) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(\sigma_1(u; X), \sigma_2(u; X), \dots, \sigma_n(u; X)) \frac{q^n}{n!}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 6. *Let α and q be two indeterminates. We then have*

$$A_n \left(\frac{1}{1-q} - \alpha, \dots, (n-1)! \left(\frac{1}{1-q^n} - \alpha^n \right) \right) = n! \left(\frac{1}{1-q^n} - \alpha \right) \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} (1-q^i)^{-1}$$

and

$$A_n \left((1-\alpha)u, \dots, (n-1)! \left(\sum_{k|n} ku^{n/k} - (\alpha u)^n \right) \right) = n! (p_n(u) - \alpha u p_{n-1}(u)),$$

where $p_n(u) := \sum_{j=0}^n p(n, j) u^j$.

Proof. We put in identity (5) $x_{1,0} = 1$, $x_{1,j} = q^{-j}(1-\alpha)$ for $j \geq 1$ and $x_{i,j} = q^{-j}$ for $i \geq 2, j \geq 0$, and use identity $B_{n,k}(1!, 2!, 3!, \dots) = \frac{(n-1)!}{(k-1)!} \binom{n}{k}$ (Lah numbers). We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} b_n(1) &= (n-1)! (1-\alpha^n) q^{-n}, \quad b_n(i) = (n-1)! q^{-n}, \quad i \geq 2, \\ \rho_n(q; X) &= \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} b_n(i) q^{ni} = (n-1)! \left(\frac{1}{1-q^n} - \alpha^n \right), \\ p(n, k; X) &= q^{-k} \sum_{\pi(n,k), k_1=0} 1 + q^{-k} \sum_{\pi(n,k), k_1 \geq 1} (1-\alpha) \\ &= q^{-k} \sum_{\pi(n-k,k)} 1 + (1-\alpha) q^{-k} \sum_{\pi(n-1,k-1)} 1 \\ &= q^{-k} [p(n-k, k) + (1-\alpha) p(n-1, k-1)], \end{aligned}$$

where $p(n, k)$ is the number of partitions of n into k parts, which satisfy

$$p(n, k) = p(n-k, k) + p(n-1, k-1).$$

Thus, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=n}^{\infty} p(j, n; X) q^j &= q^{-n} \left(\sum_{j=n}^{\infty} p(j, n) q^j - \alpha \sum_{j=n}^{\infty} p(j-1, n-1) q^j \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{1-q^n} - \alpha \right) \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} (1-q^i)^{-1}, \end{aligned}$$

which gives the first identity.

For the second identity, we take $x_{1,0} = 1$, $x_{1,j} = 1-\alpha$ for $j \geq 1$ and $x_{i,j} = 1$ for

$i \geq 2, j \geq 0$, in relation (6) to get

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_n(1) &= -(n-1)!(\alpha^n - 1), \quad b_n(i) = (n-1)!, \quad i \geq 2, \\
 \sigma_n(u; X) &= n! \sum_{k|n} b_k \binom{n}{k} \frac{u^k}{k!} = -(n-1)!(\alpha u)^n + (n-1)! \sum_{k|n} k u^{n/k}, \\
 p(n, k; X) &= p(n, k) - \alpha p(n-1, k-1),
 \end{aligned}$$

thus

$$\sum_{j=0}^n p(n, j; X) u^j = p_n(u) - \alpha u p_{n-1}(u),$$

which provides the second identity. □

4. Generalized Universal Bipartition Theorem

In this section, we provide a generalization of identity (4) and deduce some known identities. Let us start with the following example: how do we partition (2, 3) into different parts? Let $p(2, 3, k)$ be the number of partitions of the bi-partite number (2, 3) into k parts, $k = 1, \dots, 5$ and $p(2, 3)$ be the total number of partitions of (2, 3). We have

$$\begin{array}{l}
 (2, 3) \\
 \text{-----} \quad p(2, 3, 1) = 1 \\
 (0, 1) + (2, 2) = (0, 2) + (2, 1) = (0, 3) + (2, 0) = (1, 0) + (1, 3) = (1, 1) + (1, 2) \\
 \text{-----} \quad p(2, 3, 2) = 5 \\
 (0, 1) + (0, 1) + (2, 1) = (0, 1) + (0, 2) + (2, 0) = (0, 1) + (1, 1) + (1, 1) = \\
 (0, 1) + (1, 0) + (1, 2) = (0, 3) + (1, 0) + (1, 0) \\
 \text{-----} \quad p(2, 3, 3) = 5 \\
 (0, 1) + (0, 1) + (0, 1) + (2, 0) = (0, 1) + (0, 1) + (1, 0) + (1, 1) = \\
 (0, 1) + (1, 0) + (1, 0) + (0, 2) \\
 \text{-----} \quad p(2, 3, 4) = 3 \\
 (0, 1) + (0, 1) + (0, 1) + (1, 0) + (1, 0) \\
 \text{-----} \quad p(2, 3, 5) = 1
 \end{array}$$

$$p(2, 3) = \sum_{k=1}^5 p(2, 3, k) = 1 + 5 + 5 + 3 + 1 = 15.$$

Theorem 7. Let $X = (x_{i,j,s}), i, j, s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, be a sequence of indeterminates with $x_{0,0,s} = 0$, $\Pi(m, n, k)$ the set of all nonnegative integers $k_{i,j}$ satisfying (2) and (3) and $\Pi(m, n) := \bigcup_{k=1}^{n+m} \Pi(m, n, k)$ the set of all nonnegative integers satisfying (2). For every partition of the bi-partite number (m, n) into k parts, we set

$$\mathbf{p}(m, n, k; X) := \sum_{\Pi(m,n,k)} \prod_{i=0}^m \prod_{j=0}^n x_{i,j,k_{i,j}}.$$

Then we have

$$F(t, u, \omega; X) := \sum_{m, n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m+n} \mathbf{p}(m, n, k; X) \omega^k \right) t^m u^n = \prod_{i+j \geq 1} \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} x_{i,j,s} (\omega t^i u^j)^s \right).$$

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} F(t, u, \omega; X) &= \sum_{m, n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m+n} \mathbf{p}(m, n, k; X) \omega^k \right) t^m u^n \\ &= \sum_{m, n \geq 0} \sum_{k=0}^{m+n} \left(\sum_{\Pi(m, n, k)} t^{\sum_{i=0}^m i \sum_{j=0}^n k_{i,j}} u^{\sum_{j=0}^n j \sum_{i=0}^m k_{i,j}} \omega^{\sum_{i=0}^m \sum_{j=0}^n k_{i,j}} \prod_{i=0}^m \prod_{j=0}^n x_{i,j,k_{i,j}} \right) \\ &= \sum_{m, n \geq 0} \sum_{\Pi(m, n)} \left(\prod_{i=0}^m \prod_{j=0}^n x_{i,j,k_{i,j}} (\omega t^i u^j)^{k_{i,j}} \right) \\ &= \prod_{i+j \geq 1} \left(\sum_{k_{i,j}=0}^{\infty} x_{i,j,k_{i,j}} (\omega t^i u^j)^{k_{i,j}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 8. Let $A = (a_{i,j,s})$, $i, j, s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, with $a_{i,j,s} = 0$ or 1 for $(i, j) \neq (0, 0)$ and let $\mathbf{p}(m, n, k; A)$ be the number of partitions of (m, n) into k parts whose number $y_{i,j}$ of parts which are equal to (i, j) belongs to the set $Y_{i,j} = \{s : a_{i,j,s} = 1\}$, $i, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, $(i, j) \neq (0, 0)$. Then

$$F(t, u, \omega; A) := \sum_{m, n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m+n} \mathbf{p}(m, n, k; A) \omega^k \right) t^m u^n = \prod_{i+j \geq 1} \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} a_{i,j,s} (\omega t^i u^j)^s \right).$$

For $x_{i,j,s} = 1$ for all $i, j, s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, $(i, j) \neq (0, 0)$, Theorem 7 becomes:

Corollary 9. Let $\mathbf{p}(m, n)$ be the number of partitions of the bi-partite number (m, n) with $\mathbf{p}(0, 0) = 1$ and $\mathbf{p}(m, n, k)$ the number of partitions of (m, n) into k parts, with $\mathbf{p}(0, 0, 0) = 1$. Then

$$\sum_{m, n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m+n} \mathbf{p}(m, n, k) \omega^k \right) t^m u^n = \prod_{i+j \geq 1} (1 - \omega t^i u^j)^{-1}.$$

Remark 10. Let $(y_{i,j})$, $i, j = 0, 1, \dots$, be a sequence of indeterminates and let $x_{i,j,s} = \frac{1}{s!} \left(\frac{y_{i,j}}{i!j!} \right)^s$, $i, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, we have

$$\mathbf{p}(m, n, k; X) = \sum_{\Pi(m, n, k)} \prod_{i=0}^m \prod_{j=0}^n \frac{1}{k_{i,j}!} \left(\frac{y_{i,j}}{i!j!} \right)^{k_{i,j}} = \frac{A_{m,n,k}}{m!n!},$$

where

$$A_{m,n,k} := A_{m,n,k}(y_{0,1}, y_{1,0}, \dots, y_{m,n}),$$

and

$$F(t, u, \omega; X) = \sum_{m,n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m+n} A_{m,n,k} \omega^k \right) \frac{t^m u^n}{m! n!}.$$

From Theorem 7, we obtain

$$F(t, u, \omega; X) = \prod_{i+j \geq 1} \left(\sum_{k_{i,j} \geq 0} \frac{1}{k_{i,j}!} \left(\omega y_{i,j} \frac{t^i u^j}{i! j!} \right)^{k_{i,j}} \right) = \exp \left(\omega \left(\sum_{i+j \geq 1} y_{i,j} \frac{t^i u^j}{i! j!} \right) \right).$$

From the two expressions of $F(t, u; \omega, X)$, we retrieve the exponential partial bi-partitional polynomials:

$$\sum_{m,n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m+n} A_{m,n,k}(y_{0,1}, y_{1,0}, \dots, y_{m,n}) \omega^k \right) \frac{t^m u^n}{m! n!} = \exp \left(\omega \left(\sum_{i+j \geq 1} y_{i,j} \frac{t^i u^j}{i! j!} \right) \right);$$

see [2, pp: 454–457].

5. Universal Multipartition Theorem

More generally, a multipartition of order r of $\mathbf{n} = (n_1, \dots, n_r)$, different from $\mathbf{0} = (0, \dots, 0)$, of nonnegative integers, is a non-ordered collection of nonnegative integers $(x_i^{(1)}, \dots, x_i^{(r)})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$, whose sum equals $\mathbf{n}$. In a partition of an r -partite number $\mathbf{n}$, let $k_{\mathbf{i}} := k_{i_1, \dots, i_r}$ be the number of ordered r numbers that are equal to $\mathbf{i} = (i_1, \dots, i_r) \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n_1\} \times \dots \times \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n_r\}$, $(i_1, \dots, i_r) \neq \mathbf{0}$, such that

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^{n_1} \dots \sum_{i_r=0}^{n_r} i_j k_{i_1, \dots, i_r} = n_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, r. \tag{7}$$

For the partition of $\mathbf{n}$ into k parts, we add

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^{n_1} \dots \sum_{i_r=0}^{n_r} k_{i_1, \dots, i_r} = k. \tag{8}$$

Let $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n})$ be the number of partitions of the r -partite $\mathbf{n}$ with $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{0}) = 1$ and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k)$ the number of partitions of the r -partite number $\mathbf{n}$ into k parts, with $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{0}, 0) = 1$.

Theorem 11. *Let $X = (x_{\mathbf{i},s})$, $\mathbf{i} = (i_1, \dots, i_r) \in \mathbb{N}^r$, $\mathbf{i} \neq \mathbf{0}$, $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, be a sequence of indeterminates with $r + 1$ indices, with $x_{\mathbf{0},s} = 0$, $\Pi(\mathbf{n}, k)$ the set of all nonnegative integers $k_{i_1, \dots, i_r}$ satisfying (7) and (8) and $\Pi(\mathbf{n}) := \bigcup_{k=1}^{n_1 + \dots + n_r} \Pi(\mathbf{n}, k)$*

the set of all nonnegative integers solutions of (7). For every partition of $\mathbf{n}$ into k parts, we set

$$\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}; k, X) := \sum_{\Pi(\mathbf{n}, k)} \prod_{\mathbf{i}=0}^{\mathbf{n}} x_{\mathbf{i}, k_{\mathbf{i}}}.$$

Then

$$F(\mathbf{t}, \omega; X) = \sum_{\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{1}} \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k; X) \omega^k \right) \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{n}} = \prod_{\mathbf{i} \cdot \mathbf{1} \geq 1} \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} x_{\mathbf{i}, s} (\omega \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{i}})^s \right).$$

where $\mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{n}} := t_1^{n_1} \dots t_r^{n_r}$, $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{1} := n_1 + \dots + n_r$, $\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0} \Leftrightarrow n_1 \geq 0, \dots, n_r \geq 0$.

Proof. We have the following

$$\begin{aligned} F(\mathbf{t}, \omega; X) &= \sum_{\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{1}} \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k; X) \omega^k \right) \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{n}} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0}} \sum_{k=0}^{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{1}} \left(\sum_{\Pi(\mathbf{n}, k)} \left(\prod_{\mathbf{i}=0}^{\mathbf{n}} x_{\mathbf{i}, k_{\mathbf{i}}} \right) \omega^{\sum_{i_j \leq n_j} k_{\mathbf{i}}} \prod_{j=1}^r t_j^{\sum_{i_j \leq n_j} i_j k_{\mathbf{i}}} \right) \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0}} \sum_{\Pi(\mathbf{n})} \left(\prod_{\mathbf{i}=0}^{\mathbf{n}} x_{\mathbf{i}, k_{\mathbf{i}}} (\omega \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{i}})^{k_{\mathbf{i}}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

and exploiting $x_{\mathbf{0}, 0} = 0$, the last expression becomes

$$\prod_{\mathbf{i} \geq \mathbf{0}} \left(\sum_{k_{\mathbf{i}} \geq 0} x_{\mathbf{i}, k_{\mathbf{i}}} (\omega \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{i}})^{k_{\mathbf{i}}} \right) = \prod_{\mathbf{i} \cdot \mathbf{1} \geq 1} \left(\sum_{k_{\mathbf{i}} \geq 0} x_{\mathbf{i}, k_{\mathbf{i}}} (\omega \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{i}})^{k_{\mathbf{i}}} \right).$$

□

For $x_{\mathbf{i}, s} = a_{\mathbf{i}, s} \in \{0, 1\}$ for all $\mathbf{i} \in \mathbb{N}^r$, $\mathbf{i} \neq \mathbf{0}$, $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, we obtain:

Corollary 12. Let $A = (a_{\mathbf{i}, s})$, $\mathbf{i} \in \mathbb{N}^r$, $\mathbf{i} \neq \mathbf{0}$, $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, with $a_{\mathbf{i}, s} = 0$ or 1 and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k; A)$ be the number of partitions of $\mathbf{n}$ into k parts whose number $y_{\mathbf{i}}$ of parts which are equal to $\mathbf{i}$ belongs to the set $Y_{\mathbf{i}} = \{s : a_{\mathbf{i}, s} = 1\}$, $\mathbf{i} \in \mathbb{N}^r$, $\mathbf{i} \neq \mathbf{0}$. Then

$$F(t, u, \omega; A) := \sum_{\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{1}} \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k; A) \omega^k \right) \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{n}} = \prod_{\mathbf{i} \cdot \mathbf{1} \geq 1} \left(\sum_{s \geq 0} a_{\mathbf{i}, s} (\omega \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{i}})^s \right).$$

For $x_{\mathbf{i}, s} = 1$ for all $\mathbf{i} \in \mathbb{N}^r$, $\mathbf{i} \neq \mathbf{0}$, $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, we obtain:

Corollary 13. Let $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n})$ be the number of partitions of the r -partite number $\mathbf{n}$ with $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{0}) = 1$ and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k)$ the number of partitions of the r -bipartite number $\mathbf{n}$ into k parts, with $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{0}, 0) = 1$. Then

$$\sum_{\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0}} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\mathbf{n}\cdot\mathbf{1}} p(\mathbf{n}, k) \omega^k \right) \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{n}} = \prod_{\mathbf{i} \cdot \mathbf{1} \geq 1} (1 - \omega \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{i}})^{-1}.$$

Consequently

$$\sum_{\mathbf{n} \geq \mathbf{0}} p(\mathbf{n}) \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{n}} = \prod_{\mathbf{i} \cdot \mathbf{1} \geq 1} (1 - \mathbf{t}^{\mathbf{i}})^{-1}.$$

Remark 14. If we take $t_1 = \dots = t_r = t$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i \geq 1} (1 - \omega t^i)^{-\binom{i+r-1}{r-1}} &= \sum_{n \geq 0} \sum_{k=0}^n \left(\sum_{n_1 + \dots + n_r = n} \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k) \right) \omega^k t^n \\ &= \sum_{n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{n_1 + \dots + n_r = n} \mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{n}}(\omega) \right) t^n, \end{aligned}$$

and more generally, for nonnegative integers $a_1, \dots, a_r$ and $t_1 = t^{a_1}, \dots, t_r = t^{a_r}$, we obtain

$$\prod_{i \geq 1} (1 - \omega t^i)^{-f(i,r)} = \sum_{n \geq 0} \left(\sum_{a_1 n_1 + \dots + a_r n_r = n} \mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{n}}(\omega) \right) t^n,$$

where

$$\mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{n}}(\omega) = \sum_{k=0}^{a_1 n_1 + \dots + a_r n_r} \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{n}, k) \omega^k,$$

and where $f(n, r)$ is the number of solutions of the integer equation

$$a_1 n_1 + a_2 n_2 + \dots + a_r n_r = n.$$

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